

ENERGY SPATIAL DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN FOR MALAWI

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Abstract

Malawi's electrification rate is one of the lowest in the SADC region at 19%. The increased penetration of off grid electrification options has made it difficult to track the access rate in real time. The need for up to date data is increasing as the 2030 target for achieving universal access is fast approaching.

It is therefore, proposed that an integrated Spatial Data Management System for the energy sector should be developed to address the challenges of data capture, archiving, analysis and reporting. A system architecture and entity relationship diagram has been proposed. A work breakdown structure has also been proposed to ensure a more focused and logical approach to the roll out of the Spatial Data Infrastructure.

It is expected that the fully functional SDI will unlock financing for investment in the energy sector. It will also improve the accuracy of reporting of the access rate as per the national and international requirements.

1. Introduction

This report provides a rapid assessment of the spatial data management situation in Malawi. It also provides a roadmap for development and management of the spatial data infrastructure.

1.1. Overview of the Energy Access Situation in Malawi

Malawi is a land locked country with an estimated population of 20.4 million (National Statistics Office, 2019). The country's total installed capacity is 550MW with a majority of power coming from hydro. 100 megawatts are generated from solar PV making the country one among those fully relying on renewable power supply. The current peak demand is 460MW and is expected to increase to 525MW by 2025 and 750MW by 2030 (Government of Malawi, 2017).

Electrification of the country is currently at 19% comprising of 12.4% from the grid and 6.6% from off-grid solutions. Government intends to rapidly increase the electrification rate to achieve universal access by 2030 (Government of Malawi, 2018)

Over 85% of the population relies of biomass energy (Government of Malawi, 2023). This provides a high potential for increasing the adoption of clean cooking fuels and technologies.

1.2. Objectives

The main objective is to develop an Energy Spatial Data Management System for Malawi which is user friendly and accessible by June 2024.

The project to develop the Energy Spatial Data Management System will have the following specific objectives:

- a) To review existing databases, laws, project and infrastructure requirements, training needs and administrative forms.
- b) To design business processes for capturing, validating and archiving data.
- c) To carry out a prototype SDI configuration, setup, implementation, data import and pretesting.
- d) To refurbish and modernise the SDI back-end Offices.
- e) To Procure and install computer hardware and software.
- f) To increase public awareness and capacity building.
- g) To operate and maintain an updated Spatial Data Management System.

1.3. Problem Statement and Rationale

The Ministry of Energy has been implementing various reforms to attract investment in power generation and supply (Government of Malawi, 2018). However, the reforms have not resulted to significant improvements in the power market as there have been policy reversals and shifts along the way.

On the other hand, electricity access has remained low at 19% with 12.4% through grid connections and the remainder through off grid solutions. Malawi intends to achieve universal access to electricity by 2030 as espoused in the sustainable development goals and the medium term implementation plan (Government of Malawi, 2021; Korkovelos et al., 2019). While it is easy to track grid electrification, the Ministry has been having challenges to track access through off grid solutions.

There is also an emergence of the need for increased usage of clean cooking fuels and technologies and productive uses of electricity going beyond access (SEforALL, 2022a). Further to that, Covid-19 brought in a new dimension into the understanding of energy for health (SEforALL, 2022b). Therefore, electrification of public institutions including health facilities and schools is becoming a main issue.

Under such circumstances, the Ministry identified lack of an Energy Data Management System as one of the challenges leading to unsound policy formulation, uninformed policy and investment decisions which have an overall impact on the socio-economic development of the country. This Project aims at filling this gap by preparing a Spatial Energy Data Management Plan which will lead to development of the Energy Data Management System to be used as an interface between the Ministry of Energy and stakeholders in sharing energy data that will inform various developments in the country. The Plan covers all processes from data collection; storage; update; communication and dissemination; system operation and maintenance; data governance; data security; and data quality assurance.

2. Stakeholders

A stakeholder mapping shall be undertaken to understand the primary roles. Table 1 presents a preliminary list of the stakeholders by their anticipated role in the SDI.

The following are stakeholders identified for this Project:

Table 1: Role of Various Stakeholders

Hosting Institution	Sources of data	Development Partners/ Financiers	Independent Power Producers (IPPs)/ Developers	Industry Associations	Academia
Ministry of Energy	National Statistics Office (NSO); Malawi Energy Regulatory Authority (MERA); Electricity Supply Corporation of Malawi Limited (ESCOM); Ministry of Health; Ministry of Agriculture; Ministry of Education; Ministry of Transport; and Ministry of Mining.	World Bank United Nations Development Program (UNDP) GIZ United States Agency for Aid and International Development (USAID) European Union (EU)	JCM Power Serengeti Energy Cedar Energy Limited Mulanje Hydropower Limited	Renewable Energy Industries Association of Malawi (REIMA); Electrical Companies Association of Malawi (ELCAMA); Consumer Association of Malawi (CAMA); and Malawi Engineering Institution (MEI)	Mzuzu University (MZUNI); Malawi University of Science and Technology (MUBAS); Lilongwe University of Agriculture and Natural Resources (LUANAR); Malawi University of Science and Technology (MUST); and University of Livingstonia (UNILIA)

3. Actors

Various actors will be assigned roles to play in the SDI and rights to perform certain functions. While these actors will be allowed access to the backend, others will be provided with access to a dashboard which will contain a tracker on the performance of various indicators in the energy sector as per local, regional and international obligations. Table 2 provides a summary of roles to be performed by each actor.

Table 2: Definition of roles for various Actors

Actor	Role (s)
System Administrator	Upkeep, configuration and reliable operation of the SDI
Editors	Creating, editing and updating data

Database Administrators	Overall management and upkeep of the database
Cartographers	Designing, creating and updating maps
Registered Users Internal	Viewing and editing data
Public Users	Viewing data
Registered Users Within Government	Viewing data
International Reporting Obligations	Viewing data

4. Governance

The governance structure will consist of three levels namely; Steering Committee; Technical Committee and Implementation Unit.

4.1 Steering Committee (SC)

The Steering Committee (SC) will provide strategic direction to the project. It will also provide inter-ministerial coordination and policy guidance, oversee implementation of policy decisions, approve work plans and budgets for the project and also monitor progress. It will be chaired by the Principal Secretary (PS) of Ministry of Energy with other members coming from relevant and key ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs).

4.2 Technical Committee (TC)

A Technical Committee (TC) will be established under the SC to provide technical advice for implementation of the Project. It will review and recommend the work plans and budget to the SC and carry out M&E of project activities. It will be chaired by the Director of Electricity of Ministry of Energy with other members, Directors or Technical personnel coming from relevant and key ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs).

4.3 Implementation Unit (IU)

The IU will be responsible for day to day management of the project activities. Specifically, the IU will coordinate implementation of project activities detailed in the Energy Data Management Plan.

5. Software Policy

The SDI will fully utilise open source software approved by the Ministry of Energy with functionalities that are user-friendly and platform that would be able to provide support during development, use and update of the system.

6. Data Policy

In order to attain effective data governance, the Ministry of Energy will apply formal guidelines to manage the SDI and will assign staff to implement the system. The Ministry

data administrator will be assigned a leadership role and oversight for the activities of data governance.

The Ministry understands that the value of data is increased through widespread and appropriate use and it diminishes through improper use, misinterpretation, and unnecessary access restrictions. The Ministry of Energy will protect data assets through security measures that assure proper use of data when accessed. Every data item will be classified by the relevant data steward to have an appropriate access level. Data access will be conducted in accordance with the policies established by the Ministry of Information.

In accordance with Access to Information Act, anyone can access and use data from the Ministry’s SDI platform while adhering to security levels assigned to the data. Data usage falls into the categories of update, read-only, and external dissemination.

Authority to update data shall be granted by the appropriate data steward only to personnel whose job duties specify and require responsibility for data update. This restriction is not to be interpreted as a mandate to limit update authority to members of any specific group or office but should be tempered with the Ministry’s desire to provide excellent service to the public and international organizations.

7. Standards Policy

The Ministry will adopt and use ISO 191 standards in developing and managing the SDI.

8. User/Functional Requirements

Stakeholder consultations will be undertaken to understand various user requirements. For a start, a brainstorming exercise was undertaken and Table 3 summarises some of the user stories worth considering as the SDI is being designed.

Table 3: Functional Requirements

User Story Reference	Expectations	Acceptance Criteria
1.	As a private developer, I want to visualize electricity generation projects disaggregated into Grid and Off-grid including their location, capacity, LCOE and CAPEX e.t.c, so that I should be able to make investment decisions	Given that technical, economic and geospatial data is available in the database, when I chose the sites, the system should provide a summary report of technical, economic and financial parameters for each site
2.	As a user from academia, I would like to have a demo version that can be used to train students without affecting the live system.	With the available open source data, a separate working environment will be provided guiding users to the demo version.

User Story Reference	Expectations	Acceptance Criteria
3.	As a user from the Ministry of Finance, I would like the SDI to assist me in justifying the approval of development projects and allocation of budget ceilings.	Given that data will be validated through credible means before being accepted into the SDI, I will recommend allocation of budget ceilings when the proposed project is ranked in the top 2.
4.	As a user from the Development Partner community, I would like to have data that can easily be interfaced or merged with data from other countries. I would also like to be able to track progress of achieving SDG 7.	Given that spatial is available in the database, The system should allow for download of customised data which can be integrated or used to update other platforms.
5.	As a user developing and managing public infrastructure, I would like to see planned investments and wayleave corridors and assess proximity for access and minimisation of conflicts.	Given that spatial is available in the database, When I choose to view the network for a particular area, The system should also show location of existing and planned public infrastructure (roads, schools, hospitals, police.
6.	As a Planner in the Ministry of Energy, I want to visualize the spatial distribution of the current and future electricity transmission and distribution network overlaid on a map, So that I can determine the infrastructure required to expand the network	Given that spatial data is available in the database, When I choose to view the network for a particular area, The system should provide digitized maps showing the network including network parameters for HV, MV and substations
7.	As an editor, I want the system to provide user friendly interface to upload and update data in various formats including c.sv, shp, tiff e.t.c	Given that upload and update template is available, when I edit the fields, the system should be able to allow input data from the required formats and changes on the platform should be visualized
8.	As an IPP I want to see potential sites for developing power generation infrastructure/power plants as well as	Given national geospatial data, I should see point locations of all potential power generation sites and indicating type of

User Story Reference	Expectations	Acceptance Criteria
	the quality, type, size, ownership/proprietorship of the site and/or location.	potential power generation technology, size, quality, site ownership/licensing progress upon clicking of a point and see nearest substations and transmission network
9.	As an energy planner, I would like to see the cheapest and least cost electrification option of a site/community or district and visualize and see cost projections	Given available geospatial data I should see areas that do not have access to electricity and their distances from the nearest national or minigrd as well as show least cost electrification technologies and show electrification costs, graphs and charts upon clicking the area with no electricity access.
10.	As a public user, I should be able to query and download energy data of interest such as tables, analysis spreadsheet reports, charts and graphs	After visualizing geospatial data, I should be able to download visualized graphs, charts and other shapefiles as well as spreadsheets.
11.	As a registered user, I should have a high level dashboard containing key performance indicators of success	
12.	As a registered user, I should be able to send actions to line managers and wait for feedback within a specified time	
13.		

9. Data Requirements

Table 4: Data Requirements

Dataset	Source	Link	Coverage	Format	Year	Resolution	Category/ Theme	Do we have already?
National Transmission network	igea_ESCOM		National	Shape file	2023	N/A	Electricity/ Power	Yes

District Boundaries			National	shapefile	2022		Administration	Yes
National Distribution network	igea_ESCOM		National	Shape file	2023	N/A	Electricity/Power	Yes
Population Census	NSO		National	Shape file	2018	N/A	Population	Yes
Electricity access	NSO	http://www.nsomalawi.mw	National	Xls Shape file	2023	N/A	Population	Yes
Energy Demand Forecast	MoE	http://www.energy.gov.mw	National	xls	2022	NA	Energy	yes
Total Energy Supply (TES)	MoE	http://www.energy.gov.mw	National	xls	2022	NA	Energy	yes
Total Final Consumption (TFC)	MoE	http://www.energy.gov.mw	National	xls	2022	NA	Energy	yes
National Water Resources	MWS	MoE	http://www.energy.gov.mw	Shapefile	xls	2022	NA	Energy
Mini Grids	MoE	MoE		National	shp	2022	NA	
Power Plants	EGENCO							
Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) Data	Worldbank	www.worldbank.org	national	shapefile	2020	N/A	Energy	Yes

10. Database Design, System Architecture and UI/UX

ERD

11. Budget

The estimated cost of developing the SDI is USD 450,000 which is expected to be funded by SEforALL and GEAPP with part of project management costs including monitoring and evaluation being funded by the Government of Malawi.

Table 5: Budget

Project Phase	Requirements	Estimated Budget (US)
1. Inception Phase	Consultancy fees, DSA, Conference facilities, Travel costs	49,500.00
2. Design Phase	Consultancy fees, DSA, Conference facilities, local and international travel costs, procurement of computer hardware and software, office refurbishment	217,000.00
3. Configuration Phase	Consultancy fees, DSA, Conference facilities	32,000.00
4. Implementation Phase	Consultancy fees, DSA, Conference facilities, hosting costs	94,000.00
5. Support Phase (remote and onsite)	Consultancy fees, DSA, local and international travel costs	10,000.00
Operating costs	Communication, printing, rentals, utilities	47,500.00
Total Budget		450,000.00

12. QA, Testing and Review

Qualified IT/GIS specialists in the Ministry of Energy will check, test, review and validate the system throughout the process in order to ensure that relevant codes and standards for geospatial data bases are followed and adhered to. In this, all issues requiring medications or changes in the infrastructure will be identified and resolved.

13. Monitoring and evaluation

The Project will require monitoring and evaluation before, during and after implementation, for both planning and execution of the various project activities and the measurement of impact after project implementation. In addition, all project related data and records will need to be properly captured, stored and disseminated as appropriate. The services of a Monitoring and Evaluation officer shall thus be required within the IU to manage the monitoring & evaluation activities of the project including facilitating the development of practical indicators and means of capturing the required data throughout the project's life.

14. Hosting, System Maintenance and Code Management

The SDI is expected to be hosted in the Cloud (Fleming, 2023). Terms of reference will be prepared to detail the requirements for cloud-hosting which will be used to identify and procure the hosting organization.

15. Support

Support in the following areas will be required

- i. Data collection, processing and analysis;
- ii. Data storage and archiving;
- iii. Data dissemination and communication; and
- iv. Data quality assurance and control.

16. Capacity Building and Training

In the process of developing and use of the data management infrastructure, various stakeholders will be trained. The Ministry of Energy IT and technical personnel, as a hosting institution, will have to be taken through all the processes through on the job training so that they fully understand the platform. Other stakeholders, as data providers and users of the platform, will also need to be oriented on how to navigate and visualise the front end so that they should be able to provide feedback on required changes and/or updates to the system.

17. Dissemination and communication

Communication and information dissemination for the energy spatial data will be done through meetings, workshops, Ministry of Energy official websites, radio and televisions broadcasting stations including road shows. These will aim to create awareness of the platform to stakeholders who would have an input into the process of developing as well as updating the infrastructure.

18. Project schedule

19. Work Breakdown Structure

20. Expected Outputs from a Fully Functional SDI

It is expected that the SDI will have the following capabilities as derived from the training that was carried out:

- Geospatial data access;
- Geospatial analysis;
- Visualization of geospatial data; and
- Provide a friendly user interface.

21. Policy Insights and Conclusion

The following policy insights were drawn from the partial assessment that was carried out:

- SDI sustainability requires legal and regulatory support.
- Institutional ownership is critical for keeping the SDI up to date.
- An up to date SDI increases investment and project financing.
- Continuous capacity building and knowledge sharing is key.
- Adherence to the national and international standards eases harmonisation and scalability.

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